

An Overview: Integrated Farming System

N.B. Bhati^{1*}, P.B. Rathod¹, P.P. Makwana¹, B.C. Barot²

¹Polytechnic in Animal Husbandry (PAH), Kamdhenu University (KU), Rajpur (Nava), Himmatnagar-383010

²College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Kamdhenu University, Rajpur (Nava), Himmatnagar-383010.

Abstract

The integrated farming system is a multidisciplinary whole-farm strategy that is extremely effective in addressing the challenges of small and marginal farmers. These systems are well worth investigating as a method of supplying nutrients/fuel for the family, lowering fossil fuel burning and methane production, and so reducing environmental pollution. It is a desirable mono-enterprise alternative since it is both economically and environmentally sound. Better employment generation with integrated farming and more net return from Integrated Farming System than agriculture alone and better income generation and better benefit cost ratio. IFS itself is important for sustainable development of farmer by improving yield, economic return, employment generation, nutritional security and livelihood.

Introduction

The country's population is expected to reach 1660 million by the year 2050 and for which 349 million tonnes of food grains will be required. It is anticipated that land area available in 2050 would be 137 million hectares. It is urgently necessary to increase agricultural crop yield from its current level to satisfy this need. The focus should be on vertical expansion by boosting productivity by using the resources available and selecting the finest enterprises because there is no more room for land to be expanded horizontally for the cultivation of agricultural operations. The income from cropping alone is hardly sufficient to sustain the farmer's family in case of small and marginal farmers; who constitute 80.3 per cent of agricultural population with only 36 per cent of area operated. With decline in farm size due to explosion of population, it would be increasingly difficult to produce enough food for the family by the end of 21st century. India is the land of marginal and small farmers, the average size of farm land holdings is 1.16 hectares (Syamala, 2012). By combining several farm companies and recycling agricultural residues and by-products on the farm itself, the method aims to increase

revenue and employment from small holdings. IFS (integrated farming system) has revolutionized conventional farming of livestock, aquaculture, horticulture, agro-industry and allied activities (Chan, 2006).

What is IFS?

Integrated system is the combination that reduces erosion, increases crop yields, soil biological activity and nutrient recycling, intensifies land use, improving profits, help to reduce poverty, malnutrition and strengthen environmental sustainability (Gupta *et al.*, 2012). An integrated farming system focuses on the strategic pairing of one or more enterprises and the efficient recycling of residual trash for improved resource management with small and marginal farmers to increase revenue and provide employment for family labourers in the off-seasons (Behera *et al.*, 2001).

Why IFS?

Integrated farming system aims for increased productivity, profitability, sustainability, balanced food, recycling of resources, solving energy crises, income round the year, adoption of new technology, fuel and fodder crises, clean environment, avoiding deforestation, increased employment generation, input-output efficiency, enhanced opportunity for agriculture-oriented industries and standard of living of the farmers (Gill *et al.*, 2008). Generation of wastes and by-products from plants and animals are transferred between enterprises, thereby reducing the need for external inputs such as feeds and crop nutrients (Little and Edwards, 2003).

Objectives of IFS

- To make sure that available resources are used voluntarily, conserved, and that agricultural waste is effectively recycled within the system
- To maintain sustainable production system without damaging resources/environment
- To develop farming system model including both primary and auxiliary enterprises for various farming conditions.
- To achieve agro-ecological equilibrium through the reduction in the build-up of pests and diseases, through natural cropping system management and the reduction in the use of chemicals
- Given the limitations imposed by resources and the environment, to enhance the wellbeing of individual farm families by boosting the productivity of their agricultural systems.

Advantages of IFS

The advantages of IFS include pooling and sharing of resources/inputs, efficient use of family labour, conservation, preservation and utilization of farm biomass including nonconventional feed and fodder resources, effective use of manure/animal waste, regulation of soil fertility and health, income and employment generation for many people and increased economic resources. It gives a variety of items and increases space usage. The IFS is a component of the plan to guarantee the sustainable use of the environment for both present and future generations.

Components of IFS

There are different following components in IFS:

- Agriculture, Cattle, Poultry, Sheep and goat, Fish, Pigs, Biogas, Fodder production, Solar energy, Duck rearing, Kitchen gardening, Vermiculture, Sericulture, Horticulture and forestry

Role of IFS in improving soil health and nutrient cycling

IFS play an important role in improving the soil health by increasing the nutritional value of soil. The availability of N, P, K, and other mineral nutrients as well as changes in soil physical qualities are advantages of using livestock manure in crop development. The application of livestock manure increases soil organic matter content, and this leads to improved water infiltration and water holding capacity as well as an increased cation exchange capacity. IFS play an important role in improving the soil health by increasing the nitrogen, phosphorous, organic carbon and microbial count of soil and thus, reduce the use of chemical fertilizers (Walia and Kaur, 2013). The re-cycling of organic wastes for fish culture serves the dual purpose of cleaning the environment (by avoiding the problem of waste disposal) and providing economic benefits (Oladosu *et al.*, 1990).

Integration of subsystems in farming system

IFS deal with utilization of wastes and residues. It may be possible to reach the same level of yield with proportionately less input in the integrated farming and yield would be interestingly more sustainable because the waste of one enterprise becomes the input of another leaving almost nothing to pollute the environment or to degrade the resource base. To put this concept to practice efficiently it is necessary to study linkages and complementarities of different enterprises in various farming systems. The knowledge of linkages and complementarities will help to develop farming system (integrated farming) in which the waste of one enterprise is more efficiently used as inputs in another with the system. IFS correlated with different subsystems in farming system like, agriculture, Agro-forestry, aquaculture and animal husbandry. All subsystems are dependent on each other.

Combinations of Different Farming System

Conclusion

IFS is an eco-friendly approach provide better utilization of waste, improve production, profitability and soil health. It is increase water efficiency and minimize used of harmful chemical fertilizers and chemicals. Better conservation of soil and water. It is beneficial option of mono-enterprise as it is economically and environmentally sound practice. Better employment generation with integrated farming and more net return from IFS than agriculture alone and better income generation and better benefit cost ratio.

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